

Retrospective Harmonisation of the KULT Slovak Cultural Surveys

A practical guide to data preparation, and considerations for research
automation and prospective ex ante and international harmonisation

Daniel Antal

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Retrospective Harmonisation of KULT Surveys

We use the KULT summary documents to re-create the necessary metadata of the KULT microdata files and to create checkpoints. These PDF files contain the Slovak variable labels for each survey's module and columns and the sum of numeric values, which will be used as checksums when we read the raw data into R.

Tip

Latest working version: [Retrospective Harmonisation of the KULT Surveys](#) on the [Digital Music Observatory](#) website with [epub](#) and [pdf](#) downloads. The [source](#) file is always the latest.

For reference: [DOI](#). See source documents and version history on [GitHub](#).

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Rationale

To ensure that answers from respondents surveyed in different settings carry minimal methodological errors and biases and can be meaningfully compared, both data producers and secondary users combine surveys from different sources, that is, they harmonize survey data. Generally, they do so at different stages of the survey lifecycle. Data producers mostly employ harmonization ex-ante, when designing and implementing comparative studies (input harmonization) and when processing the survey data in preparation for their public release (ex-ante output harmonization). [...] Secondary users apply harmonization methods retrospectively to already released data files." (Wysmulek, Tomescu-Dubrow, and Kwak 2022)

The [Open Music Europe](#) project aims to become a data producer or co-producer using novel statistical methods that combine governmental data with privately held (music industry) data (See our [Memorandum of Understanding](#) (Ministerstvo kultúry SR and [Open Music Europe 2023](#)) and the more detailed statistical program (Antal 2023a).) Our most immediate target for harmonisation is the KULT (enterprise or institutional surveys). To suggest beneficial and easy-to-implement, forward-looking, ex-ante modifications, we first need to carry out a retrospective or ex-post analysis to understand the data's opportunities and weaknesses better.

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MINISTERSTVO KULTÚRY SLOVENSKEJ REPUBLIKY KULT(MKSR) 5 - 01

Registrované ŠÚ SR
č. Vč. 993/2014 z 12. 12. 2013

**ROČNÝ VÝKAZ
O HUDOBNOM TELESE
A UMELECKOM SÚBORE
za rok 2014**

Spravodajská jednotka vyplní výkaz v elektronickom štatistickom systéme MK SR v termíne do 6. 3. 2015.

Ochrana dôverných údajov je zaručená zákonom č. 540/2001 Z. z. o štátnej štatistike v znení neskorších predpisov.

Rok	Mesiac	IČO
1	4	1
		2

Kód štatistickej územnej jednotky	
S	K

SK NACE	Názov hlavnej činnosti
	Hudobné telesá a umelécké súbory v SR

Názov spravodajskej jednotky

P S Č	Adresa sídla spravodajskej jednotky (obec, ulica a číslo)

Working with the PDF documentation

It is possible to work with pdf files in R with the [tabulizer](#) package, which can create a fully reproducible workflow, but in our case, it would be a prolonged process because we need to work with many PDF files. Instead, we converted the PDF files to a Word document and copied the tabular information into Excel. In [tabulizer](#), you would have to figure out the coordinates of the table in the partly graphical PDF file and then read it into R. When you work between Word and Excel, you do this visually with a mouse.

I Love PDF MERGE PDF SPLIT PDF COMPRESS PDF CONVERT PDF ALL PDF TOOLS

Every tool you need to work with PDFs in one place

Every tool you need to use PDFs, at your fingertips. All are 100% FREE and easy to use! Merge, split, compress, convert, rotate, unlock and watermark PDFs with just a few clicks.

- Merge PDF**: Combine PDFs in the order you want with the easiest PDF merger available.
- Split PDF**: Separate one page or a whole set for easy conversion into independent PDF files.
- Compress PDF**: Reduce file size while optimizing for maximal PDF quality.
- PDF to Word**: Easily convert PDF to Word into easy to edit DOC and DOCX documents. The converted WORD document is almost 100% accurate.
- PDF to PowerPoint**: Turn your PDF files into easy to edit PPT and PPTX slideshows.
- PDF to Excel**: Pull data straight from PDFs into Excel spreadsheets in a matter of seconds.
- Word to PDF**: Make DOC and DOCX files easy to read by converting them to PDF.
- PowerPoint to PDF**: Make PPT and PPTX slideshows easy to view by converting them to PDF.
- Excel to PDF**: Make EXCEL spreadsheets easy to read by converting them to PDF.
- Edit PDF**: Add text, images, shapes or freehand annotations to a PDF document. Edit the size, font, color and position.

Translations

Because I do not speak Slovak, I used DeepL to understand what happened in the PDF files. We will not need this step in our project because we work with native Slovak speakers. Eventually, we will create bilingual labelling, but we will do it differently because of our need for consistency. Adding the translation offers a way to understand the tidy data (table) concept.

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PDF to Word

NO OCR ✓
Convert PDFs with selectable text into editable Word files.

OCR Premium
Convert scanned PDFs with non-selectable text into editable Word files.

2010 Kult 5 Hudobne telesa - s...

Convert to WORD

deepL.com/translator/files

DeepL Translator DeepL Pro For Business Download for Windows it's free PRO @reprex.nl

Translate text 31 languages | Translate files .pdf, .docx, .pptx | DeepL Write AI-powered edits

Slovak (detected) → English Standardwoordenlijst

Drag your PDF, Word (.docx), PowerPoint (.pptx), or text (.txt) file here
or
Select from your computer

English translation ready
2009 Kult 5 Hudobne telesa - sumar en.docx

From Word to Excel

In our case, the information in the PDF file is stored as text and numbers and not as a scanned picture; therefore, we do not need OCR software to guess what the image of letters and numbers means. We have a usable Word file and can select the tables carefully, ensuring all headings are chosen.

1. MUSIC ENSEMBLES AND PERFORMANCES MODULE		I r	Total
		8	1
Musical ensemble / artistic ensemble		1	14
Concerts/performances of the reporting ensemble in Slovakia total		2	418
in that 1	on the domestic scene	3	235
	on the non-domestic scene	4	164
Concerts of guest ensembles ¹	from SR	5	35
	from abroad	6	17
of which (from year 2)	classical music	7	365
	populer music	8	0
	Jazz	9	16
concerts/performances of the reporting ensemble in the Slovak Republic by genre	brass music	10	1
	folk music	11	1
	Other	12	97
Concerts/performances for children and youth (from year 2)		13	73
Concerts/performances abroad total		14	203

Many conversion utilities can convert a PDF file into an Excel spreadsheet file. We work in Word because this way, we can avoid the same problem that we did not work with the `tabulirzer` R package: the converter utility does not for sure what a margin is and what is already part of a table. In Excel, your columns will not be aligned, rendering the conversion of a larger table useless. (I repeat the same procedure with the English language translations, as you will see below.)

If you open the example Excel file, you will see examples of already well-copied data. You can use them to copy and paste a header to the top of a new sheet, in this case, the sheet made in the KULT-5 Excel file for the 2010 data.

	label_1_sk	label_2_sk	label_3_sk	var_numbeichecksum	label_1_en	label_2_en	label_3_en	var_numbeichecksum
1								
2								
3								
4								
5								
6								
7								
8								
9								
10								
11								
12								
13								
14								
15								
16								
17								
18								
19								
20								
21								
22								
23								

I used straightforward column names: `label_1_sk` for the first Slovak language labels, `label_2_sk` for the second, and `label_3_sk` for the third. In the KULT PDF for 2007 the table was broken into three columns (because of the merged summary columns), but later,

it was more, so I had to add a `label_4_sk`. There were two critical columns: a numbering, which serves as a guide to the columns of the microdata CSV file, and the actual sum of numeric information reported by the statistical subjects.

For example, **Concerts/performances of the reporting ensemble in Slovakia total** stitched with **on the domestic scene** corresponds to the 3rd column in Module 1 of the KULT-05 survey in 2010. The total of this statistic is 235. I call the number three `var_number_sk` and the total value a `checksum_sk` because it will be used to check if we read in the microdata correctly. The `_sk` suffix is used to record that this information is coming from the Slovak version of the Word file; in the unlikely case that you made a copying mistake, it is better to know where to search for the correspondence with the authoritative files. For labelling, the `_sk` and `_en` suffixes serve a natural purpose; I do not want to mix up Slovak and English-translated label elements.

label_1_sk	label_2_sk	label_3_sk	label_4_sk	var_number	checksum	label_1_en	label_2_en	label_3_en	label_4_en	var_number	checksum_en
1. OFFERED PLACES AND VISITORS											
MODULE											
Total number of premieres											
				25	39						
	works of Slovak authors			26	35						
	in that	works by foreign authors		27	4						
Total number of music recordings in Slovakia											
				28	53						
		for media on sound carriers		29	45						
	in that			30	8						
2. OFFERED PLACES AND VISITORS											
MODULE											
Number of places offered											
				1	113 880						

In a tidy data table, every observation is a row, and every variable is a column. In this case, the observation corresponds to a variable (*a column in the microdata_file*); our KULT-05 summary PDF is observing what can be found in the original microdata. If you work with translations, you must ensure that **Concerts/performances of the reporting ensemble in Slovakia total** are in the same line in all languages because they observe the meaning of the same variable in the microdata.

The variables, or the columns, must be well-aligned. For example, the `var_number_sk` must always fall into the same column. Because the table is adjusted from the top left-hand corner, I drag the columns from left to right whenever something does not align. Because the lower Module 2 table has more columns than the upper Module 1, I dragged the `var_number_sk` and the `checksum_sk` in the upper table until it aligned well with the lower Module 2 and Module 3. I called the extra column `label_4_sk` in the Slovak version and `label_4_en` in English.

At this step, I also remove the footnotes. This step is not critical; when in doubt, leave them be. Removing them in R programmatically would potentially need much exception handling (if the footnotes appear in different locations), so I just do it this way because I have to work in Excel on the alignment of the columns.

Now everything is almost tidy; the most critical information, i.e., where we find the `Concerts/performances of the reporting ensemble in Slovakia total` in the microdata, is aligned with the labels of every other variable.

label_1_sk	label_2_sk	label_3_sk	label_4_sk	var_numbei	checksum	1. MUSIC ENSEMBLE PERFORMANCE'S MOBILE	Total	checksum_en
1	1	14				1	14	1
2	2	418				2	418	2
3	3	235				3	235	3
4	4	164				4	164	4
5	5	35				5	35	5
6	6	17				6	17	6
7	7	365				7	365	7
8	8	0				8	0	8
9	9	10				9	10	9

The last step is breaking up merged columns in Excel. Combining columns is a good practice for human readability. It will not work well with a computer-actionable table because the computer does not know intuitively what the merging means. So, I point the mouse to the select all table field (the little triangle between the A heading for the first column and the 1 row label for the first row), and when the entire sheet is selected, I navigate to unmerge cells and break them up.

As a result, the Excel table is less readable for humans but more understandable for the processing workflow. It is a bit disturbing that the variable labels (i.e., the description of the meaning of the variable) is fragmented into 1, 2, 3, or 4 cells, but that will be an easy fix: in R, I will concatenate them into a single label, for example, adding together elements `Concerts/performances of the reporting ensemble in Slovakia total` separated by `-` with `on the domestic scene` in row 8 of my Excel table (corresponding to `KULT05.M1.3`, or the 3rd column of Module 1 in the `KULT05` microdata.) Because we will work with thousands of labels, this concatenation is better done in R; it would take a very long time in Excel, and it is likely that the administrator of that Excel file would get tired and make a mistake at some point.

Remember that all of this post-processing in R is possible if the rows and columns are well aligned. If `Concerts/performances of the reporting ensemble in Slovakia total` are not well aligned with `on the domestic scene`, then the entire codebook and crosswalk table will be useless.

In the tidyverse

```
require(tidyverse)

# I name the label fragments as a group for easier referencing:
labels_sk <- c("label_1_sk", "label_2_sk", "label_3_sk", "label_4_sk")
labels_en <- c("label_1_en", "label_2_en", "label_3_en", "label_4_en")

kult_5_metadata_2007 <- readxl::read_excel(
  file.path(Open_Music_Europe_stories_folder,
            "data-raw", "KULT5",
            "KULT5_example.xlsx"),
  sheet="2007"
) %>%
fill(
  # When label cells were merged, there are empty cells
  # now that I fill from top down.
  starts_with("label"), .direction = "down"
) %>%
unite (
  # I select any variable that is part of the labels_sk
  # group and concatenate them with the - separator
  col = label_sk,
  any_of(labels_sk), sep = " - ") %>%
unite (col = label_en,
  any_of(labels_en), sep = " - ") %>%
mutate (
  # When I concatenated empty cells, I got - NA
  # texts in the previous step, I remove them:
  label_sk = gsub(" - NA", "", label_sk),
  label_en = gsub(" - NA", "", label_en) )
```

I am selecting randomly 12 rows (with the highest numbers):

```
kult_5_metadata_2007 %>%
  top_n(12)
```

Selecting by checksum_en

```
# A tibble: 12 x 6
  label_sk          var_number_sk checksum_sk label_en var_number_en checksum_en
  <chr>              <dbl>         <dbl> <chr>          <dbl>         <dbl>
1 Koncerty / vyst~ 2             399 Concert~      2             399
2 Koncerty / vyst~ 3             291 Concert~      3             291
```

3	Koncerty / vyst~	5	173	Concert~	5	173
4	Koncerty / vyst~	6	572	Concert~	6	572
5	Koncerty / vyst~	12	140	Concert~	12	140
6	v tom koncerty,~	15	166	includi~	15	166
7	v tom koncerty,~	25	347	includi~	25	347
8	Vystúpenia v za~	33	143	Perform~	33	143
9	Koncerty / vyst~	34	144	Concert~	34	144
10	Koncerty / vyst~	51	716	Concert~	51	716
11	Celkový počet d~	52	469	Total n~	52	469
12	v tom - diel za~	54	363	in that~	54	363

We have a variable map!

```
# For readability I select only the English side and
# in a different order:

kult_5_metadata_2007 %>%
  top_n(2) %>%
  select ( all_of(c("var_number_en", "checksum_en", "label_en")))
```

Selecting by checksum_en

```
# A tibble: 2 x 3
  var_number_en checksum_en label_en
      <dbl>         <dbl> <chr>
1             6         572 Concerts/performances in the country total (yr. 2 +-
2            51         716 Concerts/performances at home and abroad (r. 6 + 34~
```

The `var_number_en` tells me that in the relevant module I need to look for this column number to get the information. If I sum all the reported values, I should get the `checksum_en` value which must be equal to the `checksum_sk` value. The `_sk` and `_en` refers to using the original Slovak file or the DeepL translated English version; the numbers should be the same in both.

Labels and Variable Names

There are only two hard things in Computer Science: cache invalidation and naming things. – Phil Karlton

Our entire PDF processing is motivated to create a variable map and to name columns consistently in the different microdata tables the same way if the meaning of the numbers is semantically the same in them. We cannot leave human curation out of the equation now. Sometimes, there may be a slight difference in the label's wording (even as much as a word is Capitalised or not capitalised), but the data user must know if the semantic meaning

of this variable is the same. In other words, did the KULT survey item change over the years?

The best way to do it is to explicitly collect all variations and give a canonical label to the exact same ones. Because I used DeepL, there is no guarantee that every time I ran the DeepL translator, it used the exact same English synonyms for the same Slovak word. Because the Slovak text is the authoritative source, we must ensure that when a label is deemed to be identical to another one in Slovak (and has the same, final, canonical label), then the very same English translation is used for such a text in every instance.

Labelling is important for tabular and visual data presentations and serves as a semantic guide for the analyst. Working with labels to reference the data is not possible in a programmatic way, so we must create an easy-to-type shorthand for each variable. For example, abbreviate “Total concerts in Slovakia” with “concerts_total_sk”.

In the tidyverse dialect of R, snake_case is preferred to other languages’ CamelCase, so we give snake case variable names. When naming the variables, the following considerations are used:

- Avoid non-ASCII characters, such as Slovak special characters, because they may not be available in all programming IDEs
- Because programming languages are derived from English, it is easier to use English language names; the use of English variable names will increase code readability
- Avoid any characters that computer languages interpret with a special meaning or represent differently, and never use a `space`, `!`, `~`, `*`, `%`, `+` and other mathematical symbols in variable names (Pro tip: use similar filenames on your computer so that they remain portable between Linux, Mac, BSD and Windows systems and cloud storages.)
- The same concept, such as `concert` or `total` should always be `concert` (or performance, but consistently) and `total` (and not `sum`, or the other way around, only `sum` but not `total`)
- For the abbreviations of sentences or statements, use a practical word order to benefit from the use of `tidyselect` functions such as `starts_with`, `ends_with`; for example, it is common practice to put the language or geographic reference as a suffix to the end (and not as a prefix to the beginning), such as `concert_total_sk`, enabling the selector `ends_with(“sk”)`
- Whenever possible, avoid the use of capitalisation; the selectors will not work if Slovakia is sometimes abbreviated as `SK` and sometimes as `sk` or even `Sk`.

It is likely that the variable labels and variable names will be canonised after using the data a bit.

Identification of Observational Units and Namespaces

One of the potential problems in the creation of an integrated, longitudinal (or panel) dataset is that the *Štátna filharmónia Košice* may sometimes be labelled as `ŠTÁTNA FILHARMÓNIA KOŠICE`. It is even more frustrating when one space is replaced with two

Štátna filharmónia Košice because it is almost impossible to detect for a human reader in a big spreadsheet.

Identity matching is very important; if we create statistics that must involve all philharmonic orchestras but not chamber orchestras, the *Štátna filharmónia Košice* must always be selected from our 15 tables or definitively stated “missing”. An observation (row) cannot hide behind a Štátna filharmónia - Košice label variation.

To avoid identification problems, the Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic assigns the organization identification number (IČO) to all types of legal entities, entrepreneurs and public authorities. Whenever the IČO is present, we will retain it, but the use of IČO is not optimal for our use case. Some reporting units may not have an IČO number (because they are internal units of a larger entity, such as the public broadcaster). If we want to compare Czech and Slovak orchestras, we need a more universal identifier.

Linking data about observational units

The Virtual International Authority File (VIAF) identifier serves as a global identifier in the world’s national libraries and other libraries that use the same referencing as their national library. The VIAF record of [Štátna filharmónia Košice](#) shows the accepted and preferred names of the orchestra in many global libraries.

Beyond that, we can also immediately see how we can find information about the orchestra in many countries:

It is immediately apparent that using this identifier goes far beyond the ability to join datasets properly. Using the VIAF ID as an identifier, we may find further datasets or information carriers unknown to us and outside of our possession via the web of data or the semantic web.

An alternative to VIAF is the ISNI. ISNI serves a different purpose; in this case, we can see the name changes going back to Czechoslovakia since the orchestra’s inception in 1968. While VIAF is controlled by the national libraries (and its use is free, provided a librarian provides an entity with a VIAF ID), the ISNI is free for all who pay a registration fee.

A third alternative is Wikidata, which uses the QID to identify entities, such as textual references in Slovak, English, and German Wikipedias, as a permanent ID. Its use is free but with caveats.

The great advantage of Wikidata QIDs, is that they serve as a reconciliation tool among many global and national IDs, for example, in the example below we can immediately find how to connect the VIAF and ISNI files of , and go further, for example, to the [Bibliothèque nationale de France](#).

Which is the best to use? There is no clear answer to this question; therefore, we created a namespace in a survey harmonisation program. We collect all name variations of observational units, select a canonical Slovak and a canonical English version, and add various identifiers for the unit.

For data processing and the creation of statistics, internally we can change VIAF, QID, ISNI, and even BNF identifiers if we remain consistent. If we use VIAF for Štátna filharmónia Košice, we should always refer to them with their VIAF ID [viaf:123337893](#) . If we refer to Slovenská Filharmónia with [isni:000000011421725X](#), we should always refer to them with ISNI.

It is very practical to have a QID to extend our knowledge base and database because it can

add different entry points to other relational or graph databases. We generally recommend to record at least one of VIAF and ISNI, QID, and when applicable, IČO for Slovak data.

Variable semantics

```
require(retroharmonize)
kult5_raw <- read_surveys (
  file.path(KULT_raw_folder, 2007:2022, "KULT-5.csv"),
  .f = "read_csv"
)
```

Linking data about the variables

A dataset can only be used by an analyst if that person understands the contents of the dataset. The tidy dataset concept ensures that an analyst understands the table's structure. When every observation is in a single row, and every variable is in a column, the dataset is tidy and ideally stored in a relational (tabular) database. Internalizing the knowledge of tidy data is important because users of unreflected data still try to bring the dataset to a tidy format when they wrangle it in a spreadsheet editor.

More semantic information is needed to create derived tables, statistics, or modify tables. We need not only to know that `total_concert_audience` is a number but also if the unit measured is a number or a thousand. We must understand if budgetary variables are expressed in SKK or EUR. When we have a dimension for the `female`, `male`, and `non-binary` categories, we need to know if `F` means female or something else. Datasets are usually very hard to reuse if such information is lost, so we are developing an R package that stores this information in a way that easily converts data together with the metadata to the Data cube W3C global, interoperable standard.

Perhaps the most important semantic information is a precise description of the data: it relates to `concerts`, `audiences` and `total` (not average) values. Often, we would like to calculate the Slovak audiences and compare them to neighbouring Czech, Hungarian, or Austrian values. In Slovakia, Czechia, and Hungary, such data will be found in national knowledge centres under the `koncert` heading, while in Austria, it will be under `Konzert` and in global databases, most likely under `concert`.

Controlled vocabularies and subject terms, just like authority files on institutional and person names, enable us to link the information to a variable column in a spelling- and even language-independent way. For example, marking a variable with the [sh85030620](#) subject heading of the Library of Congress Subject Headings will make it understandable in many libraries of the world that we are looking for information on concerts.

Statistical agencies and their Statistical Data and Metadata eXchange, or survey archives such as GESIS, use such controlled and linked vocabularies to create new data catalogues or match data. The global W3C DCAT 2.0 definition and its European version, the DCAT-AP,

allow an automatic connection among European open data portals and APIs. The Open Music Europe project develops tools and the Digital Music Observatory in a way that our datasets are equipped with such linking.

Data linking is not only a way to expand our human knowledge, or the knowledge of our intelligent software agents. The links refer to permanent, well-known definitions that are usually created in two formats, depending on the visitor type (human through a browser or a software agent via an application.) Data linking makes our datasets and data catalogue truly interoperable (humans and intelligent artificial agents can use them alike) and reusable (precise documentation will be available for decades and in many natural languages.)

Like in the case of namespaces, Wikidata is a controlled vocabulary reconciliation tool among many languages and national knowledge centres. Therefore, we will usually add the following information to a `concert_total_audience_sk` variable: A descriptive label in the Slovak and English language, at least one reliable knowledge-centers controlled vocabulary term(s) for the concepts, and the relevant Wikidata entries for further reconciliation among countries and systems.

We do not recommend reliance only on Wikidata; while it is the easiest and fastest to find definitions on Wikidata, statistical agencies, libraries, and music archives generally maintain

wikidata.org/wiki/Q182832

English Not logged in Talk Contributions Create account Log in

Item Discussion Read View history Search Wikidata

Are you using or editing Wikidata, but sometimes struggling with how data is organized? Join us at the online **Data Modelling Days**, from November 30th to December 2nd, to discuss with the Wikidata community about your data modelling challenges!

concert (Q182832)

live performance of music
live music | qig | live concert

↳ In more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	concert	live performance of music	live music qig live concert
Hungarian	koncert	No description defined	hangverseny
Dutch	concert	live muziekvoering	popconcert ultraoening concertvoering optreden concerten
German	Konzert	live-Darbietung von Musik	Rockkonzert Popkonzert Musikveranstaltung

All entered languages

Statements

instance of form of event

Wikipedia: 89 items

- af: ʔabɔɔɔɔ ʔabɔɔ
- az: Konser
- be: Канцэрт
- bg: Концерт
- bn: ʔabɔɔɔɔ
- bs: Koncert
- ca: Concert
- cs: Koncert
- da: Koncert (begivenhed)
- de: Koncert (Veranstaltung)
- el: Κονσέρ
- en: Concert
- eo: Koncerto
- es: Concierto
- et: Kontsert
- eu: Kontzertu
- fa: ʔabɔɔɔɔ ʔabɔɔ
- fi: Konsertti
- fr: Concert
- gl: Concierto

wikidata.org/wiki/Q182832

Identifiers

GND ID	43174747	1 reference
National Library of Israel J9U ID	987007553057905171	1 reference
Library of Congress authority ID	sh85536820	subject named as Concerts 1 reference
National Library of Latvia ID	000112785	0 references
NDL Authority ID	00568886	0 references
NL CR AUT ID	ph121790	subject named as koncerty 0 references

more precise and purpose-built vocabularies. Whenever we do not see such a conceptual description ([link](#)) immediately, starting with the Wikidata entry is a good start.

Further work

WP3: Survey harmonisation

Concept harmonisation

WP1: Data gap identification

Identifying targetted concepts

WP2: Data gap identification

Identifying targetted concepts

WP4: Software ecosystem

The development of the [retroharmonize](#) R package was a generalisation of harmonisation problems with CAP surveys conducted in Hungary, Slovakia and Croatia (in the CEEMID project, a predecessor of [Open Music Europe](#)) with Eurobarometer surveys (Antal 2021). In the later generalisation, we used the Afrobarometer and the Arab Barometer survey data. Methodologically, the workflow is similar to the workflow of Marta Kołczyńska (Kołczyńska 2022), who was a contributor to the first release of the package. It was also used with the CEEMID/Digital Music Observatory Music Professional Surveys.

The KULT survey program's data sets new requirements. Unlike the Eurobarometer, Afrobarometer and Arab Barometer, this survey program was not published for microdata access, and the level of documentation is lower; the number of surveys is high.

In [Open Music Europe](#), we aim to produce novel datasets that need further functionality for ex-ante harmonisation. As the package's name suggests, it is a retrospective harmonisation package and will not make ex-ante harmonisation fully reproducible. The new functionality aims to improve data linking and documentation and add support to the concept harmonisation part of the general research workflow. These additions enhance the usability of the retrospective harmonisation.

We identified two important features that are not specific to survey harmonisation and will eventually be detached to further generalised packages.

The [dataset](#) package aims to make native R datasets more reusable and interoperable by retaining more provenance, semantic and structural metadata and providing easier import/export/exchange with standardised data catalogues and their datasets (Antal 2023c). This package improves the portability, interoperability, and reusability of our results. For more detailed description of the planned work see (Antal 2023b).

The planned crosswalk package aims to make relabelling and recording easier. This is a general task that is necessary for administrative data sources, too.

The DDIwR package (Dusa 2021) aims to manage better the surveying workflow and the archival of surveying documents. We are still investigating to what extent this is helpful for **Open Music Europe**, while it certainly adds to the future-proof qualities of our work, the exploitation of these additional features is more straightforward in a long-term or permanent program (such as KULT itself, not **Open Music Europe**.)

Dataset

WP5: Music Observatory prototype

Namespaces

Global namespaces and authority files are, by design, machine-actionable; they can be read by humans, activating a html representation for human browsing and an RDF serialisation for data applications. We will encourage the use of at least two PIDs for each observational unit, following the best practices that will be elaborated in greater detail in 5.1.

- We will use either ISNI or VIAF identifiers for natural and legal persons. The use of ISNI is paid, and the organisation itself must initiate it. The use of VIAF is free because it is a public service of the Slovak National Library, but it goes through a curation process. For our purposes, they are equally good and they can be used interchangeably.
- We will also use a QID for data coordination. The QID is a globally unique identifier in Wikidata and Dbpedia. They are used in the statistical, research and cultural heritage domains as temporary or necessary global IDs when the use of an authority file is not possible or takes a long time (for example, we have to encourage each orchestra to obtain its own ISNI number.)

The use of Wikidata is getting more and more common among knowledge organisations and even EU organisations. Originally developed as a reconciliation tool for Wikipedia, Europeana already recognised its value for pan-European data harmonisation in 2015. Since that, it had been used as a decentralised, curated, shared authority control system in several European countries. We think that VIAF is the most suitable authority control, but the flexibility and functionality of Wikidata makes it a worthy parallel system in itself (Bianchini, Bargioni, and Pellizzari di San Girolamo 2021; Veen 2019; Rossenova, Duchesne, and Blümel 2022) We reached out to the Wikimedia Foundation and *WMSK*, former official legal name *Wikimedia Slovenská republika* to not only use their open source product, i.e, Wikibase for authority control reconciliation, but as a tool to push our knowledge and our namespace to the Wikidata. (Fagervig 2023)

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